

OBTAINING ADHESIVES FROM LOCAL RAW MATERIALS

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Annotation: Adhesive materials (glues, binders, pastes) are widely used in construction, woodworking, paper production, packaging, and other industries. While synthetic polymer-based products currently dominate the market, interest in adhesives made from locally sourced raw materials is steadily growing. This article discusses the methods of obtaining and properties of adhesive materials.

Key words: adhesive oligomers, local raw materials, thermal stability, structure, polymer synthesis, viscosity, adhesive compositions, environmental friendliness.

Adhesives (glues, binders, pastes) are widely used in construction, woodworking, paper production, packaging, and other industries. The modern adhesives market is saturated with products based on synthetic polymers, but there is growing interest in producing adhesives from local raw materials. This is explained by economic accessibility, environmental safety and the possibility of creating biodegradable materials.

Local raw materials can include wood, plant waste, fruit peels, grain husks, animal products (glue, casein), and industrial byproducts. Using these resources allows us to create adhesives with specific physical and chemical properties tailored to local conditions.

Adhesives are classified by their source material:

1. Protein adhesives – derived from animal sources (collagen, casein) and plant proteins (soy protein, wheat glue).
2. Sugar adhesives – derived from starch, dextrans, and other carbohydrates.
3. Lignin- and cellulose-containing adhesives – derived from wood and plant fibers.
4. Resin and thermosetting adhesives – made from natural resins, such as pine or rosin.

The main sources of local raw materials are:

1. Wood and wood waste – bark, sawdust, and chips – a source of lignin and cellulose.

They are used to produce phenol- and formaldehyde-containing resins, as well as hydrolytic adhesives.

2. Plant products and agricultural waste – grain hulls, legume, potato, and corn starches.

They are used to produce starch and protein adhesives, as well as combined compounds with improved adhesive properties.

3. Animal proteins – collagen from skin and bones, casein from whey.

They are used in the paper and furniture industries, as well as in food packaging.

1. Production of protein adhesives

a) Protein raw materials (meat and dairy waste) are ground and hydrolyzed using enzymes or alkali.

b) The resulting solution is filtered and concentrated to the required viscosity.

c) If necessary, plasticizers and preservatives are added to increase shelf life.

2. Obtaining starch adhesives

a) Potato, corn, or wheat starch is liquefied with water and heated to a paste-like consistency.

b) Modifiers are added to improve adhesion: acids, alkalis, polyols, and organic solvents.

c) After cooling, the adhesive is prepared into a ready-to-use adhesive or concentrate for subsequent dilution.

3. Lignin and resin adhesives

a) Lignin is isolated from wood chips by alkaline hydrolysis.

b) The resulting solution is mixed with formaldehyde or other polymers to produce a strong thermosetting adhesive.

c) Used in the production of particleboard and plywood.

The advantages of using local raw materials include reduced cost of adhesives, environmental friendliness and biodegradability, and the ability to create materials with unique properties (e.g., water resistance, heat resistance, antibacterial properties).

Conclusion: The use of local raw materials for the production of adhesives is a promising direction that combines economic efficiency and environmental sustainability. Advances in plant and animal waste processing technologies make it possible to create adhesives with the required physical and chemical properties for various industries. In the future, we can expect growing interest in combined and modified adhesives based entirely on renewable resources.

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